

High Voltage Test for a Research of Reducing the Number of Aircraft Lightning Strike

Hiroyuki Tsubata¹, Takayuki Nishi¹, Hiromitsu Miyaki², Shintaro Kamiyama², Takao Okada²

¹ SUBARU Corporation Aerospace Company, ² Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA)

¹ 1-20-8, Ebisu, Shibuya, Tochigi, Japan, ² 6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka, Tokyo, Japan

¹ {tsubata.hiroyuki, nishi.takayuki}@subaru.co.jp, ² {miyaki.hiromitsu, kamiyama.shintaro, okada.takao}@jaxa.jp

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1. Abstract

Most of lightning strikes to aircrafts are thought to be triggered by the aircraft itself. When an aircraft flies near thunderclouds, leaders are formed from a local concentration of electric field on the surface of the aircraft, and one of the leaders connects to a leader that comes from thunderclouds, and then the high lightning current flows through the aircraft. The Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) and SUBARU focus on this leader initiation and are seeking the way to reduce the frequency of aircraft lightning.

High voltage impulse discharge tests were conducted for a simple shape and an aircraft shape. Both are made from aluminium. Those were suspended in the air under a relatively wide electrode ($\phi 1200\text{mm}$) with a 600-800mm gap to the ground. In general, if the discharge gap is too short, leaders won't be appeared, so that the setting of the size was considered enough to observe the leaders that propagates from the specimens. Also, uniform electric fields with Rogowski shaped electrode was used to prevent that the leaders from the electrode appear quicker than that of the specimen. Even though the results obtained in the laboratory can't be applied directly to the natural lightning to an aircraft in flight, this experiment was worth enough to realize the basic patterns of discharge phenomena of a floating object.

Two still cameras and a high-speed video camera was used to observe those discharges, and the detail sequence of how the leader was formed and growing and turned into a flashover was observed. The up-and-down method was used to estimate 50% flashover voltage, and there was a significant difference depending on the combination of the body shape, attitude, the electrical charge to the body and electrodes' polarity. The results show that the body shape, the body attitude, and the electrical charge to the body were playing the important role for a breakdown.

2. Introduction

At the present time, to avoid lightning strikes on aircraft, thunderstorms are detected by a ground facility and flight restrictions are made such as a route change. That interferes the operation of the aircraft depending on the weather. Therefore, it is hoped to develop a method to reduce the number of aircraft lightning strike. Most of the lightning strikes on aircraft are triggered by aircrafts. Recently, measures have been proposed to reduce the risk of aircraft triggered lightning by charging the aircraft. [1]

JAXA and SUBARU are conducting joint research to suppress the leader generation for aircraft triggered lightning by charging and controlling the attitude of an aircraft. Those

measures are considered to mitigate the concentrated areas of the electric field. The issues of this research are the evaluations of the discharge progress and the condition of the leader generation.

3. Definitions

Breakdown: In this paper, breakdown means electrical breakdown. A bright plasma appears after a leader connects the electrodes gap.

Leader: A continuous string of light which consists of plasma. It appears after streamers and grows from an electrode or floating objects. It has streamers in its growing head.

Streamer: A particle of light running from an electrode or floating objects firstly appears when voltage applied between the electrodes. It also appears around the leader tip. A bundle of streamers is called corona.

4. Experiment Conditions

A high electric field environment was created using an impulse generator instead of DC voltage to simulate a lightning. It was considered that the impulse is enough to investigate the difference of the discharge situation. The impulse waveform was set in consideration of SAE ARP5412B [2] and SAE ARP5416A [3]. Figure 1 shows a typical waveform. The peak time was $2.7\mu\text{s}$.

Fig. 1 Typical waveform of the applied voltage

A Rogowski shaped electrode was used to observe the leader from a suspended object. The reason was that if the electrode was sharp like a needle, the leader would be generated from the electrode faster than the object, making it difficult to observe the leader generated from the objects. The electrode was circular, $\phi 1200\text{ mm}$, and had a Rogowski curve. It was suspended 600 or 800 mm from the ground. An aluminium plate was laid on the ground and connected to the laboratory ground. A Haefely generator was used to apply a maximum of 900kV. Fig. 2 shows the experimental environment. The up-and-down method [5] was used to calculate the voltage

threshold. The step voltage was 40 kV and the number of shots in each test was 20 times.

Fig. 2 Generator and electrode

Effectiveness of charge control was considered by reviewing the literature in [1][4], and it was decided to have the charged specimen cases. However, a Van de Graaff generator as in the literature [4] was not used. Instead, an Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) Gun as shown in Fig. 3 was used to control the electrical potential of the objects since it was considered that it makes the experiment configuration simple. ESD gun can provide both positive and negative polarities.

Fig. 3 Pre-charging

The amount of the charge was measured by a surface potential meter shown in Fig. 4. The surface potential was measured before and after applying the electrode voltage.

Fig. 4 Measuring surface potential

The ambient environment during the experiment was 18-25 degrees Celsius and 9-19% humidity.

Discharges were observed by optical images and the waveform of the divider resistor voltage (An oscilloscope was connected. See Fig.2) that represents the gap voltage. The high-speed camera was used with a frame rate of 10M FPS to

record the leader extension, and still cameras were used with UV lenses for recording corona and streamer. The experimental area was darkened with a blackout curtain for camera photography.

4.1 Case1: The Lightning Rod

Before conducting the floating object experiment, a lightning rod is used for the reference of the breakdown voltages. It was placed on ground at the centre of the electrode. Electrode gap was 800mm and lightning rod length was 300mm. See Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Case1 configuration

4.2 Case 2: The T-shape object

Electrically floating objects made from aluminium were hanged in the middle of the electrode gap space. The T shaped object was made as the simplified shape of the aircraft. It has same shape tips on its nose, tail and vertical stabiliser. A combination of $\varnothing 20$ mm cylinders, 200 mm long, 60 mm high with semi-circular ends, and hanged by $\varnothing 0.8$ mm nylon strings. Two strings can make the various attitude of the object. The gap was controlled 600mm, and the T-shaped object was suspended in the middle. See Fig. 6. Attitude of T-shape object was set by pitch angle. 0deg, 15deg up, 165deg down and 180deg. When its pitch angle is 15deg up, the tips of protruding portion and nose are the same level. 165deg down is the opposite angle of 15deg.

Fig. 6 Case2 configuration

4.3 Case 3: The Aircraft-shape object

The aircraft shape was from NASA Common Research Model provided in NASA website with its vertical stabilizer was designed by ONERA. The aircraft model has 400mm length and fixed in the space by GFRP rod. See Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Case3 configuration

5. Results

5.1 The Lightning Rod

Fig. 8 is the high-speed camera image when just prior to the breakdown. In case of the electrode is positive, the leaders grew from both the electrode and the lightning rod, however, in case of the electrode is negative, the leader only grew from the lightning rod. Streamers can be observed in front head of the leaders.

The 50% threshold was calculated by up-and-down method and results of positive and negative were 596kV and -291kV respectively (Electrode voltages). Generally, it is known that when the electrode are plate and needle, the negative needle breakdown threshold is about two times larger than that of positive. The test results show a ratio of 2.05, confirming that the negative electrode (lightning rod is positive) is prone to breakdown.

The breakdown thresholds were converted to electric fields (dividing the voltage by the gap length) to compare with other test cases. When the rod tip is negative 1.19MV/m was the breakdown threshold. When the rod tip is positive 0.58MV/m was the breakdown threshold.

Fig. 8 Still camera images of the leaders in case 1 (Silhouettes of the lightning rod are superimposed.)

5.2 Breakdown process of a floating object

The typical pattern of the breakdown process of level flight attitude aircraft model in Case 3 of negative electrode were described in Fig. 9 and Table 1. Upper attachment point was the vertical stabilizer and lower attachment point was the left engine nacelle. However, the lower attachment point was varied when the aircraft attitude is level. Those were not only the right engine nacelle, but also the nose or the tail. The upper attachment point had changed depending on the aircraft attitude.

Fig. 9 Breakdown process images by a high speed camera (Silhouettes of the aircraft model are superimposed.)

Table 1 Breakdown process

Step	Upper part of the aircraft	Lower part of the aircraft
1	Streamers start from vertical stabilizer.	No sign of streamers.
2	The streamers became hazy.	No sign of streamers.
3	A leader starts.	Streamers start from engine nacelles.
4	The leader grows.	Streamers became hazy.
5	The leader still grows.	Leaders starts.
6	The leader almost attaches to the electrode.	A strongest leader almost attaches to the left engine nacelle.

In Step 1, streamers were generated at the top of the vertical stabilizer. Streamers could not be observed constantly in this early stage; those were like filamentous that means streamers were the flow of small light particles. The streamers reached to the electrode and became hazy in Step 2. Then the streamers

could not be observed but the new light start from the object again. This light spot is considered as a root of a leader. At the same time, negative streamers start at the lower parts of the object in Step 3. In Step 4 through Step 6, the upper leader grows and leached to the electrode, then breakdown happens, while at the same time, in the lower part, leaders grow from the ground plane and one of the leaders connected to the aircraft.

When the floating object was T-shape the steps of the breakdown process were the same, but streamers often observed from the top of the protruding portion when the T-shape object placed flat (place horizontally with the protruding part on top).

5.3 50% Breakdown Threshold

Breakdown threshold values (converted to electric field value MV/m: same as ambient electric field for the floating objects) in case 2 and 3 were calculated by up-and-down method. Both positive and negative thresholds without pre-charge are graphically drowned as the length of horizontal lines in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Thresholds without pre-charge cases

Every floating object's threshold is between negative and positive thresholds of lightning rod. It seems reasonable that the shape of the object of positive side (red circle) dominates the breakdown threshold. For example, the aircraft vertical stabilizer tip has very strong electric field because of its sharp edge so that the breakdown voltage of Pattern A is the lowest among the floating objects. Pattern B comes next since the T-shape protruding point is sharper than tilted pattern E and it has duller than that of pattern A. The lower part of the aircraft has uneven surfaces but multiple (Pattern C) so that it has higher threshold than Pattern A. The difference between patterns D and E is within the margin of error since the standard deviation was about 0.03 to 0.04 MV/m. The difference between Patterns E and F can be analyzed as the threshold is higher when the electric field is distributed over two red circles rather than one. Patterns F and G are within the error range. However, the threshold of positive electrode case is higher if the red circles are the same number and same shape.

This may explain by the fact that since the electrode had a finite length and it did not form a perfectly equal electric field.

Horizontal lines in Fig. 11 show the T-shaped object's thresholds (Case 2) including pre-charged cases when the negative voltage was applied to the electrode.

Fig. 11 T shape thresholds in Negative voltages

Firstly, flat position (place horizontally with the protruding part on top) was the easiest breakdown case. When its attitude changes, the breakdown voltage increases in order of 165deg down, 15deg up and 180deg. There was no breakdown observed in the case of 180 deg, instead, breakdown occurred directly between the electrode and ground. The reason is assumed that positive side (red circle) surface of 180 deg case has relatively low electric field because it was flat. When the T-shape was pre-charged in positive the threshold was not changed much. However, when T-shape was pre-charged negatively the threshold was significantly increased.

Fig. 12 shows the aircraft shape results (Case 3) including pre-charged cases.

Fig. 12 Aircraft shape thresholds in Negative voltages

If the aircraft pitches were close to the level cases, those thresholds were almost the same. Even if the negative pre-charge applied case, the threshold didn't change much because the sharp edge of the vertical stabilizer made strong electric field. When pitch attitude was 30deg, the threshold decreased, but when the 30deg pitch aircraft was pre-charged, the threshold was significantly increased. This pitch angle is large enough to shift the strongest positive electric field from vertical stabilizer to nose head of the aircraft. However, nose head shape was rounded, so that the electric field can be controlled by the charging activity.

5.4 Breakdown waveform

5.4.1 Without pre-charge cases

Fig. 13 is a graph of the typical voltage of the electrode in Case 3. "A" is the time when a leader started. "B" is the time when the breakdown path established. Those events are measured by a high-speed camera video shown in Fig. 14. Before "A", streamers were observed from around 10ns. After "A", the leader grows until the breakdown path has established. In this case, "B" is the picture of about 0.4μs before the voltage drop. Between "B" and voltage drop the voltage slightly went down.

Fig. 13 Typical breakdown waveform of without pre-charge case. A: Leader start, B: Breakdown path established.

Fig. 14 High speed camera images at A and B of Fig. 13

5.4.2 Pre-charged cases

Fig. 15 is a graph of the typical breakdown voltage when the specimen was charged in Case 3. "A" is the time when a leader started. "B" is the time when the breakdown path established. Those events were measured by a high-speed camera video shown in Fig. 16. Before "A", no streamers were observed. It

can be considered that pre-charge leaked gradually until "A". After "A", the leaders grow quickly so that it was difficult to distinguish streamers and leaders. The leader grew until the breakdown path had established. In this case, "B" occurs about 0.3 μs before the voltage drop. Between "A" and "B", a dent of the voltage was observed. This waveform suggests that when the charge leaks to some extent, a breakdown begins, and the remaining charge flows away at once while the leader grows.

Fig. 15 Typical breakdown waveform of pre-charged case A: Leader start, B: Breakdown path established.

Fig. 16 High speed camera images at A and B of Fig. 15 case

5.5 Partial breakdown

5.5.1 Without pre-charge cases

It was often observed that the floating objects had some electrical potential after the partial breakdown occurred. The still images of partial breakdown are indicated in Fig. 17. These were the negative electrode cases of case 3.

Fig. 17 Corona images without breakdown cases (Silhouettes of the aircraft model are superimposed.)

When the applied voltage is just lower than the breakdown voltage, partial breakdown occurs at the vertical stabilizer and at each tip of the body. The vertical stabilizer had the strongest partial breakdown. It can be considered that an ionization occurs at the vicinity air of the tip of vertical stabilizer, and electrons of the plasma flow into the aircraft body. That's why the aircraft charged negatively after the partial breakdown. However, as the applied voltage higher, remained potential reduced. This can be considered that the higher voltage the more partial discharges occurs in the lower side extremities. That made electrons flow out of the aircraft, then the remained potential reduced.

5.5.2 Pre-charged cases

When the floating objects are pre-charged, few partial breakdown observed in both positive and negative pre-charges. However, the remained potential reduced. It seems that the leak of the pre-charge prevents partial discharges.

Let's consider about a value of a pre-charge voltage minus a remain voltage divide by a pre-charge voltage. This parameter can be used as the ratio of leaked charges. Among the partial breakdown of negative electrode cases of case 2, when negative pre-charge applied, this leaked charges were increased with the applied voltage increased to negative. These results were shown in Fig. 18. If the object was pre-charged negatively, the electrical potential went down and it made the electric field on the tip of protruded portion lower, so that the partial discharges at the upper part of the object were not occurred. Otherwise, at the lower part of the object, the negative pre-charge made the surface electric field stronger and the electrons flew out (leaked) from the object. That's why the ratio of leaked charge increased as the applied voltage increased. The reason why the partial discharge in lower part of the object didn't occurred can be considered that the space charges leaked to the lower part of the object made the electric field in the lower surfaces weak.

Fig. 18 Ratios of leaked charges of negative pre-charge cases in case 2

Fig. 19 shows the leaked charge ratios of positive pre-charge cases. In these cases, a partial discharge wasn't observed as same as negative pre-charge cases. However, the ratio of leaked charge didn't increase with increasing negative voltage. The mechanism of the phenomenon can be considered as a following story. When the specimen pre-charged positively the electric field increased at the tip of the protruding portion. This made an ionization of the air at the vicinity of the tip. However, most of the electrons of the ionization flew into the specimen so that the light of the recombination couldn't be seen. No light was observed but the partial discharge might be occurred. This can explain a reason of the charge leaked. The

number of electrons of the ionization is limited, so that the ratio of leaked charge didn't increase.

Fig. 19 Ratios of leaked charges of positive pre-charge cases in case 2

6. CONCLUSIONS

Breakdown threshold voltage can be increased by controlling the object's attitude and charging state. This indicates that there is a possibility to narrow the flight restriction area of lightning by those measures.

Negative charging increase the breakdown threshold significantly if the shape of the most intense positive electric field side is rounded.

The shape of the part of floating object in the most intense positive electric field side may dominate the breakdown threshold.

In case the floating object was charged and there was no breakdown occurred, no partial discharge was observed.

7. REFERENCES

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8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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